

EMVA 1288 Data Sheet m0774

This datasheet describes the specification according to the standard 1288 for “Characterization and Presentation of Specification Data for Image Sensors and Cameras of the European Machine Vision Association (EMVA)” (see www.standard1288.org or the *Zenodo EMVA 1288 community*) release 3.0 with proprietary extensions from AEON. The measurements were performed with the AEON ACC2b RGB-IR, Release 5, 27.06.2014, SN 0009(HCI) . The performance parameters and estimated accuracy of the measurements are described in the technical report for the instrument, its calibration in the corresponding specification and calibration report.

Measurements performed by B Jähne, HCI, Heidelberg University and H Herrmann, AEON

Vendor	PCO
Model	edge
Serial number	61000057
Sensor diagonal	21.77 mm
Lens category	Nikon F
Resolution	2560 × 2160, 16 bit
Pixel size	6.50 μm × 6.50 μm
Sensor	Fairchild sCMOS
Sensor type	CMOS
Shutter type	Rolling
Overlap capabilities	Overlapping
Maximum frame rate	30.4 Hz
Interface type	CameraLink full

Type of data presented	Single
Operation point 1, (page 6)	
Wavelength centroid	465.8 nm
Wavelength FWHM	20.9 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 2, (page 21)	
Wavelength centroid	533.9 nm
Wavelength FWHM	31.3 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 3, (page 36)	
Wavelength centroid	630.1 nm
Wavelength FWHM	13.2 nm
Gain, offset	default
Operation point 4, (page 51)	
Wavelength centroid	848.2 nm
Wavelength FWHM	19.7 nm
Gain, offset	default
Optional data measured	
Quantum efficiency	at centered AOI 640 × 640 with 3 nm resolution

Spectral sensitivity m0796, 28.09.2015

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 1

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	23.7°C
Exposure time	1.00 ms	Camera body temperature	29.6°C
Frame rate	100.0 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	36.2°C, 0.0°C
Data transfer mode	86 MP/s, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	466 nm, 20.9 nm

Quantum efficiency

η 48.5%

Overall system gain

K 2.426 DN/e
 $1/K$ 0.412 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 3.03 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.84 DN
 σ_d 1.24 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.34 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 163
44.2 dB
7.3 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.61 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.44 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.46%
LE_{min} -0.61%
LE_{max} 0.30%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 3.81 p
0.090 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 54651 p
1294 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 1.84 e
0.044 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 26496 e
627 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 14363
83.1 dB
13.8 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 2

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	23.7°C
Exposure time	1.00 ms	Camera body temperature	29.6°C
Frame rate	100.0 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	36.2°C, 0.0°C
Data transfer mode	86 MP/s, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	534 nm, 31.3 nm

Quantum efficiency

η 57.7%

Overall system gain

K 2.378 DN/e
 $1/K$ 0.421 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 3.04 DN
 DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.84 DN
 σ_d 1.27 e
 DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.35 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 165
 44.3 dB
 7.4 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.61 %
 PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.63 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.43%
 LE_{min} -0.57%
 LE_{max} 0.28%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 3.25 p
 0.077 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 46965 p
 1112 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 1.87 e
 0.044 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 27086 e
 641 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 14451
 83.2 dB
 13.8 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 3

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	23.7°C
Exposure time	1.00 ms	Camera body temperature	29.6°C
Frame rate	100.0 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	36.2°C, 0.0°C
Data transfer mode	86 MP/s, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	630 nm, 13.2 nm

Quantum efficiency

η 58.5%

Overall system gain

K 2.354 DN/e
 $1/K$ 0.425 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 3.04 DN
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.84 DN
 σ_d 1.28 e
DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.36 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 165
44.3 dB
7.4 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.61 %
PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.85 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.43%
LE_{min} -0.58%
LE_{max} 0.27%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 3.22 p
0.076 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 46493 p
1100 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 1.88 e
0.045 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 27185 e
643 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 14431
83.2 dB
13.8 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

EMVA 1288 Summary Sheet for Operating Point 4

Type of data	Single	Gain, offset	default
Exposure control	by irradiance	Environmental temperature	23.7°C
Exposure time	1.00 ms	Camera body temperature	29.6°C
Frame rate	100.0 Hz	Intern temperature(s)	36.2°C, 0.0°C
Data transfer mode	86 MP/s, filter off	Wavelength, centr., FWHM	848 nm, 19.7 nm

Quantum efficiency

η 22.4%

Overall system gain

K 2.334 DN/e
 $1/K$ 0.428 e /DN

Temporal dark noise & DSNU

$\sigma_{y, \text{dark}}$ 3.05 DN
 DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.84 DN
 σ_d 1.30 e
 DSNU₁₂₈₈ 0.36 e

Signal-to-noise ratio & PRNU

SNR_{max} 164
 44.3 dB
 7.4 bit
 $1/\text{SNR}_{\text{max}}$ 0.61 %
 PRNU₁₂₈₈ 0.87 %

Nonlinearity

LE 0.35%
 LE_{min} -0.26%
 LE_{max} 0.44%

Sensitivity & saturation

$\mu_{p, \text{min}}$ 8.48 p
 0.201 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{p, \text{sat}}$ 120098 p
 2843 p/ μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{min}}$ 1.90 e
 0.045 e / μm^2
 $\mu_{e, \text{sat}}$ 26897 e
 637 e / μm^2

Dynamic range

DR 14157
 83.0 dB
 13.8 bit

Dark current

$\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — DN/s
 $\mu_{c, \text{mean}}$ — e /s
 $\mu_{c, \text{var}}$ — e /s

Detailed Data Operating Point 1, 466 nm

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1.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.187	0.142	0.141	0.140	0.141	0.141	0.140	0.140
0.002	0.007	0.040	0.041	0.041	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.042
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.019	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.019	0.018
0.017	0.018	0.017	0.018	0.017	0.017	0.018	0.018	0.017
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
0.012	0.011	0.011	0.010	0.011	0.011	0.010	0.011	0.011
0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017	0.017
0.016	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.015

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.011	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006	0.006
0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001

1.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 401 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 401 illumination steps.

1.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

1.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

1.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 92.9 - 97.9 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.3\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0774, 466 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	95.37	3.06	0.84	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	6286.97	126.97	33.43	5.61	17.01	0.27	50.87
20	12648.90	178.36	61.20	7.88	18.73	0.15	30.61
30	19329.83	219.79	90.29	9.71	19.24	0.10	21.31
40	25635.42	251.71	115.90	11.12	17.01	0.07	14.67
50	32282.87	280.22	142.64	12.38	0.77	0.00	0.54
60	38866.55	305.12	169.09	13.48	23.09	0.06	13.66
70	45017.55	323.77	192.75	14.31	31.93	0.07	16.57
80	51302.28	341.07	216.15	15.07	45.04	0.09	20.84
90	57795.15	356.72	241.05	15.76	61.82	0.11	25.65
100	63779.24	366.98	263.97	16.22	109.99	0.17	41.67

Detailed Data Operating Point 2, 534 nm

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2.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.191	0.147	0.146	0.146	0.146	0.146	0.146	0.146
0.000	0.005	0.037	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.039
0.005	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.008
0.013	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.012	0.012	0.012
0.015	0.016	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016
0.003	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
0.010	0.010	0.009	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
0.014	0.014	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015	0.015
0.013	0.012	0.013	0.012	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.012

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.014	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.006	0.007
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.003

2.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 401 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 401 illumination steps.

2.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

2.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

2.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 92.9 - 97.9 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 1.9\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0774, 534 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	95.42	3.06	0.84	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	6421.81	127.88	49.61	5.65	17.67	0.28	35.62
20	12882.00	179.17	90.09	7.92	19.11	0.15	21.21
30	19148.80	217.49	129.04	9.61	19.15	0.10	14.84
40	25956.68	251.31	168.33	11.11	17.25	0.07	10.25
50	32465.72	278.81	205.37	12.32	0.36	0.00	0.18
60	38763.13	301.55	237.51	13.33	24.06	0.06	10.13
70	45206.50	320.30	271.13	14.16	34.75	0.08	12.82
80	51656.26	337.37	303.43	14.91	49.90	0.10	16.45
90	57935.25	351.76	335.87	15.55	67.08	0.12	19.97
100	63926.66	361.77	369.75	15.99	108.34	0.17	29.30

Detailed Data Operating Point 3, 630 nm

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3.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.195	0.151	0.149	0.150	0.149	0.149	0.150	0.149
0.003	0.008	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.043	0.043
0.005	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
0.022	0.021	0.021	0.022	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.022
0.019	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.020
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001
0.017	0.016	0.017	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.017	0.016
0.021	0.022	0.022	0.022	0.022	0.022	0.022	0.021	0.022
0.014	0.014	0.013	0.014	0.014	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.014

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.016	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.007
0.004	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001
0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001

3.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 401 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 401 illumination steps.

3.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

3.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

3.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 92.8 - 97.8 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 2.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0774, 630 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	95.32	3.06	0.84	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	6243.70	126.13	59.04	5.57	17.53	0.28	29.69
20	12705.71	177.56	114.29	7.85	19.04	0.15	16.66
30	19185.22	216.91	168.95	9.59	18.61	0.10	11.02
40	25753.53	249.21	221.74	11.01	16.78	0.07	7.57
50	32001.67	274.51	272.41	12.13	1.05	0.00	0.38
60	38728.48	299.28	324.38	13.23	23.62	0.06	7.28
70	45119.24	317.43	371.69	14.03	33.84	0.07	9.10
80	51353.79	333.46	416.80	14.74	47.37	0.09	11.37
90	57521.96	347.34	459.67	15.35	65.49	0.11	14.25
100	63629.06	357.41	502.43	15.80	103.79	0.16	20.66

Detailed Data Operating Point 4, 848 nm

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4.1 Checks for Correctness of Measurements and EMVA 1288 Model

Gray value histogram accumulated over all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Stability check: temporal standard deviation (line) and difference of mean of two images (crosses) for all illumination steps (plot in extension of EMVA1288 standard).

Covariance coefficients of neighboring pixels averaged over the whole image sensor. Values unequal zero except for coefficient without shift, which is one, indicate some kind of preprocessing. This makes the central assumption of the linear EMVA 1288 model invalid. The gain K will then be lower and the quantum efficiency η higher than the true values.

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, dark image (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.199	0.155	0.154	0.154	0.153	0.153	0.154	0.153
0.004	0.009	0.041	0.042	0.043	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042
0.009	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.011
0.024	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.024	0.024	0.024
0.024	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.024
0.004	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003
0.014	0.015	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.015	0.014	0.014
0.027	0.028	0.028	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.028
0.019	0.018	0.018	0.018	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.019

List of covariance coefficients in 9×9 neighborhood, 70% saturation (standard deviation of coefficients for uncorrelated pixel: 0.0004):

1.000	0.019	0.009	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.007
0.005	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001

4.2 Sensitivity and Noise

Characteristics camera curve (sensitivity plot) with 401 illumination steps.

Photon transfer curve with 401 illumination steps.

4.3 Linearity

Linearity curve.

Deviation from linearity.

4.4 Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

SNR m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Signal-to-noise ratio in double-logarithmic presentation.

4.5 Nonuniformity: DSNU, PRNU, profiles, spectrograms

DSNU

Contrast enhanced dark image, range 92.9 - 98.0 DN (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units DN.

Horizontal spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

Vertical spectrogram of dark image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.14 DN.

PRNU

Contrast enhanced response image, range $\pm 2.6\%$ (not part of EMVA 1288 standard).

Logarithmic histogram of spatial deviation from mean in units %

Accumulated logarithmic histogram of absolute spatial deviation from mean in units %

Horizontal spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Vertical spectrogram PRNU at 50% saturation m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical spectrogram of response image averaged over 512 images, standard deviation of residual temporal noise is 0.038%.

Horizontal and vertical profiles (preliminary, release 3.1)

Horizontal lines DSNU m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal lines PRNU m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Vertical lines DSNU m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical lines PRNU m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Vertical profiles of dark image in units DN (2.5% of full range shown) and of response image in % deviation from mean.

Spatial variation of temporal noise (extension to EMVA 1288)

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise in DN

Logarithmic histogram of spatial distribution of standard deviation of temporal dark noise at 50% saturation in DN

Horizontal profiles residual PRNU (in extension to EMVA 1288)

Residual PRNU m0774, 848 nm, 24.09.2015

Horizontal profiles of residual PRNU for middle line in % of mean after two-point calibration with dark image and 50% saturation image for a low and high saturation level.

Table with residual inhomogeneities at different saturation levels after a two-point correction with dark image and 50% saturation image.

Saturation %	μ_y DN	σ_y DN	s_y DN	$\sigma_{y.res}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ DN	$s_{y.corr}$ %	$s_{y.corr}/s_y$ %
0	95.43	3.06	0.84	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	6006.65	123.90	58.84	5.48	17.80	0.30	30.24
20	12320.09	174.62	112.69	7.72	19.79	0.16	17.56
30	18514.88	212.70	165.87	9.40	19.26	0.10	11.61
40	25007.89	245.00	220.64	10.83	17.76	0.07	8.05
50	31266.65	269.96	271.90	11.93	0.24	0.00	0.09
60	37993.22	295.34	328.65	13.05	25.02	0.07	7.61
70	44438.85	313.98	377.23	13.88	35.65	0.08	9.45
80	50767.32	329.79	424.23	14.57	50.19	0.10	11.83
90	57141.72	343.95	472.83	15.20	68.79	0.12	14.55
100	63473.49	354.76	521.42	15.68	107.89	0.17	20.69

Comparative Evaluation with all Colors

This whole section is in extension to the EMVA 1288 standard.

Comparative characteristic curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Comparative photon transfer curve for all measured color/channel combinations.

Comparative double-logarithmic SNR curve for selected colors/channels as indicated in the legend.

Color dependency of PRNU: profile of middle row of sensor, shown as deviation from PRNU averaged over all measured colors.

Comments

Measurement of heavily used camera. Therefore some dust was on the glass window of the sensor.